

Code	Article Title	Author(s)	Journal/Conference/Source	Publication Date	Topic(s)	Relevance to the Project	Information Source for Source	Information Source for Date	Information Source for Date	Information Source for Date	Methodology	Challenges and Opportunities	Feedback	Conclusions of the Article	Notes
0003	Human factors for the next generation: Identifying barriers to 2025 Project 1000's safe and effective performance	Michael J. Griffin, David A. Bowers, and Robert A. Proctor	Proceedings of the 2001 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems	2001	<p>In this article, we aim to summarize the following issues in question:</p> <p>What are the most significant barriers to safe and effective performance in 2025?</p> <p>What are the most significant barriers to safe and effective performance in 2025?</p> <p>What are the most significant barriers to safe and effective performance in 2025?</p> <p>What are the most significant barriers to safe and effective performance in 2025?</p>						<p>More has been identified than has been identified and specific design problems.</p> <p>Human factors research is needed to address the barriers to safe and effective performance in 2025.</p> <p>The barriers to safe and effective performance in 2025 are identified and specific design problems are identified.</p>			<p>Human factors research is needed to address the barriers to safe and effective performance in 2025.</p> <p>The barriers to safe and effective performance in 2025 are identified and specific design problems are identified.</p>	